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Critical Assessment of the Impact of the Child Rights Act 2003 in Protecting Children against Child Marriage in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

National and international instruments have condemned child marriage as a human rights violation that harms girls and women who are married early, their children, their families, and globally. Even though the Nigerian government has tried to eradicate child marriage by enacting the Child Rights Act of 2003, the practice of child marriage persists, especially among the Hausa-Fulani tribe in the Northern part of Nigeria where Sharia Law is in force. There is an assertion that the Child Rights Act has sharp teeth but cannot bite, especially as each state has to pass the CRA to law before it is enforceable. Thus, early marriage is still practised in states that have yet to pass the Child Rights Act as domestic law. Furthermore, it is also suggested that the inconsistency in the law and the absence of a clear stipulation of minimum age for marriage in Nigeria is another obstacle to implementing the CRA regarding Child marriage. This paper assesses whether the laws and policies prohibiting child marriage reduce or eliminate this menace. In so doing, this paper will also examine the challenges in implementing the Act, especially regarding Child marriage. In line with this, the reaction and reluctance of some states and stakeholders will also be explored and analyzed. Thus, the researcher argues that the girl child's right concerning early marriage is not effectively protected. This paper recommends measures to adequately address the challenges regarding implementing laws and policies that will sufficiently reduce or eliminate child marriage in Nigeria.

Keywords: Child Marriage, Prohibition, Loopholes, Challenges, Human Rights violations.

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of child marriage in Nigeria is intricately connected with the nature and extent of protecting human rights in a multi-cultural and multi-religious constitutional democracy torn between different perspectives and ends. One perspective protects certain rights of human beings, including children, because they are human beings in the most robust liberal tradition. In contrast, the other perspective promotes the norms of the community that men, women and children are born into religious or cultural communities that often subordinate the interests of their members to the norms of the community. Child marriages in Nigeria illustrate how the material base of society affects the quality of protection that the recognition of human rights brings. It demonstrates how the social and legal complement each other in protecting human rights.

Nigeria belongs to the dualist school of thought regarding the reception of international law into internal law. The view is held that international law must go through legislative enactment by the Nigerian

National Assembly to become binding.¹ Since child marriage is within the whole matter of the States, domesticated international laws regarding child marriage are of no binding force in states whose customary and Islamic practices encourage child marriages. For instance, Nigeria has signed and ratified international and regional treaties regulating children's rights. These treaties have been domesticated in the form of the Child Rights Act (CRA) 2003. The CRA transforms into internal or national law Nigeria's obligations under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948; Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women 1979; Convention on the Consent of Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriage 2964; International Convention on Economic and Cultural Rights; International Convention on Civil and Political Rights; Supplementary Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, the Slave Trade and Institutions and Practices 1956; World Health Organization Constitution; Africa Charter on Human and People's Rights and Welfare of the Child 1990 and Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989. Through the National Assembly, the federal government of Nigeria enacted the CRA to provide for and protect the rights of Nigerian Children and other related matters. The CRA prohibits child marriage and betrothal of children in part III Section 21: 'No person under the age of 18 years is capable of contracting a valid marriage and accordingly, a marriage so contracted is null and void and of no effect whatsoever.' Pursuant to this, 'no parent, guardian or any other person shall betroth a child to any person.'² In contravention of the same, the CRA provides for punishment in Part III Section 23 and views the same as criminal.³ The problem is that despite being enacted at the National level, the CRA still needs to be binding on the States. The States are required to adopt the CRA for domestication as state laws formally. This is because child rights protection issues are on the Nigerian Constitution's residual list, giving States exclusive responsibility and jurisdiction to make laws relevant to their specific situations. States' laws inimical to the child's rights are also expected to be amended or annulled as may be required to conform to the CRA.⁴ Unfortunately, since the CRA was enacted in 2003, out of 36 states in Nigeria, 12 states have not yet domesticated the CRA.⁵ The implication is that within these states, child marriage will go unpunished, especially concerning states whose religion and custom allow child marriage (eg Islam and Shari'a in the Northern States of Nigeria). This paper intends to reflect on some of the challenges and shortcomings of the CRA in terms of eradicating the child marriage phenomenon, namely, the legal, cultural, religious, and socio-economic factors.

2. Who is a Child?

A child is generally seen as any person who is not yet an adult. Postulations as to the nature of a child have been advanced in specific enactments as well as social and cultural perspectives. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child defines a child as a person below the age of 18 years unless under the law applicable to the child the age of majority is attained earlier. In *Re Carlton*⁶, Cohen J. said that the meaning of the word "child" must, in every case, depend on the context in which it appears. Similarly, Article 2 of the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child states that a child is "Every human being below the age of 18 years"⁷. In the same vein, the Child's Rights Act 2003, passed into law in the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja),⁸ defines a child as a person who has not attained the age of eighteen years. However, s. 2 of the Children and Young Persons Act, enacted in Eastern and Northern regions (CYPA) defines a child as a person under the age of 14 years, while 'young person' means a

¹ Sec. 12 of the Nigerian Constitution; Frank T.M and Thiruvengadam A.K 'International Law and Constitution Making' (2003) Chinese Journal of International Law 467-476

² Part III Section 22 CRA

³ 'A person; (a) who marries a child or (b) to whom a child is betrothed or (c) who promotes the marriage of a child or (d) who betroths a child, commits an offence and is liable on conviction to a fine of N500,000 or imprisonment for a term of five years or both such fine and imprisonment.'

⁴ F E Eboibi 'Dichotomy of Child Marriage in a Democratic Nigerian Society (2010) 2(3) International Journal of Humanities 148.

⁵ Enugu, Zamfara, Adamawa, Kano, Kaduna, Bornu, Yobe, Gombe, Bauchi, Kastina, Kebi and Sokoto.

⁶ *Re Calton*

⁷ African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACRWC) 1999 Act 2

⁸ Child's Rights Act 2003 s 277

person who has attained the age of 14 years and is under the age of 17 years⁹. ILO Convention 138 defines a child as anyone below the age of 16 while, Convention 182 defines a child as anyone below the age of 18 (ILO, 1999a).

In addition, the Immigration Act states that any person below the age of 16 is a minor, while the Matrimonial Causes Act puts the age of maturity at 21 years. With respect to penal responsibility, section 50 of the Penal Code (North) states that, no act is an offence which is done by a child under 7 years of age, or a child above 7 years of age but under twelve years of age who has not attained sufficient maturity of understanding to judge the nature and consequence of such act¹⁰.

However, in Lagos State, s.2 of the Children and Young Persons Law 1973 provides that a child is a person under the age of fourteen years while a young person is one who has attained the age of fourteen years. Again, the Nigerian Labour Act 1974 defines a child as a person below fifteen years of age while the National Child Welfare Policy considers a child as a person who is twelve years of age and below¹¹.

Apart from the statutory and treaty definitions, there is also a customary definition of a child. The customary definition varies from ethnic group to ethnic group under the Nigerian socio-cultural context, the definition of a child varies widely as a result of lack of uniformity in the cultural systems. In some ethnic groups, a boy is considered to be a child until initiated into an age-grade society or until he is old enough to contribute physically and financially to community development¹².

Under the common law, the age of puberty is considered to be a boy of fourteen years, while that of a girls is twelve years. This position was confirmed in the case of *Harrod v Harrod*.¹³

The problem with age-based definitions is that they are always arbitrary and always risk being rendered obsolete by modern perceptions and findings on children. On the other hand, age represents the most objective criterion for ascertaining who falls within the framework of a child protection policy. Sadly, the disparity and uncertainty in minimum age in different circumstances and jurisdictions, which fluctuates between 7 to 21 years has made child protection a challenge. To be sure, these disparities may lead to interpretations which contradict the best interest of the child philosophy and also lead to severe discrimination of certain groups of children¹⁴. This uncertainty may also result in arbitrary decisions and impunity for abuses contained in the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC).

From the foregoing, there appears to be general consensus that any person that is not yet 18 years of age is universally considered to be a child. Thus, for the purpose of this study, the author will rely on the definition of a child contained in section 274 of the Child Rights Act (2003) which defines a child as a person who has not yet attained the age of 18 years which is indeed in line with the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child both of which Nigeria is signatory.

It is worthy to note that signing and ratifying convention and treaties constitute the major means of entering into agreement to be legally bound by it at international law.¹⁵ However, the state will ensure that their domestic constitutionally required procedures have been fulfilled. Section 12 of the said Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria requires the treaty so ratified to be transformed by the legislature before it can be admitted in Nigeria's Court.¹⁶ Section 12 (1) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria provides that 'No treaty between the federation and any other country shall have the force of law except to the extent to which any such treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly'.¹⁷ Nigeria ratified the CRC on the 16th April 1991. However, by virtue of section 12 of the

⁹ O Ogunsakin, 'Legal Prognosis of Child Labour Under the Child Rights Act: Labour Law Review' (2008) 2 Nigerian Journal of Labour Law and Industrial Relations 111

¹⁰ Penal Code Section 50

¹¹ Akwara, Soyibo and Agba, 'Law and Children's Rights Protection: The Nexus for a Sustainable Development in Nigeria'

¹² Ibid

¹³ *Harrod v Harrod* (1854) 69 ER 344

¹⁴ O Bolaji and A Adedeji, *Overview of the Rights of the Child in Nigeria* (Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies 1996)

¹⁵ I. O Babatunde, 'Treaty Making and its Application Under Nigerian Law, The Journey so Far' (2014) 3 International Journal of Business and Management Intervention 7

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ The 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

constitution, no international treaty will have the force of law in Nigeria except it has been passed by the National Assembly and ratified by a majority of the State Houses of Assembly in all the states of the Federation. Some writers have argued that the Child's Rights Act is unconstitutional because the requirements of the Constitution were not strictly adhered to in passing it into law¹⁸. It is said that the Act was rather hastily passed at the National Assembly and assented to by the President without having it approved by the State Houses of Assembly hence unconstitutional and therefore void.

Although there was some initial uncertainty as to the status of a treaty vis-à-vis the Nigerian Constitution¹⁹, the Supreme Court clarified the position and in *Chief Gani Fawehinmi v Sani Abacha*²⁰ held that with respect to obligations and entitlements, the African Charter is below the Constitution and where a conflict arises between them, the provisions of the Constitution shall prevail. Thus, in the words of Ejiwunmi JSC, no matter how beneficial an international treaty seems to Nigeria or to its citizens, it cannot have the force of law if it is not domesticated under the provisions of the constitution.²¹ The implication of this therefore is that international law cannot automatically be transformed into Nigerian Law without legislative intervention.

3. The Concept and Meaning of Child Marriage

Child marriage is a deeply entrenched social menace that has persisted across cultures and societies for centuries. Child marriage is a formal or informal union where at least one spouse is below the age of 18, which violates human rights and has terrible consequences for the children involved. The practice is more prevalent in poor and developing regions, where economic, cultural, and social factors contribute to its perpetuation.

The practice is often associated with gender inequality, particularly, as girls are disproportionately affected compared to boys.²² The roots of child marriage can be traced to religion, customs and traditions, poverty and economic constraints, and social norms that perceive early marriage as a means of securing financial stability and protecting family honour.²³ However, child marriage often leads to adverse outcomes, including health risks, interrupted education, and exposure to domestic violence and abuse.²⁴ In considering the legal perspectives on child marriage, it is important to note that International human rights instruments, such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), condemn child marriage and advocate for the protection of children from early marriage.²⁵ The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) also emphasize the need to eliminate child marriage by 2030 under Goal 5 on gender equality.²⁶ Despite these global efforts, child marriage persists due to weak legal enforcement and cultural resistance in various jurisdictions. National laws on the minimum age of marriage vary, with some countries permitting exceptions under religious, traditional or customary laws.²⁷ Furthermore, Child marriage has profound implications for the socioeconomic well-being of children and societies at large. Girls who marry early often experience restricted educational opportunities, leading to reduced economic prospects and an inevitable cycle of poverty.²⁸ Health consequences include increased risks of maternal

¹⁸ A. A Umar, H. N Abdul and Yussof C. S. Y, 'Analysis of Relevant Legal Frameworks on Child Protection in Malaysia and Nigeria' (2016) 1 UNIMAID Journal of Private and Property Law 184

¹⁹ *Ogugu v State (1996) NWLR (pt 316) 1, 30-31*

²⁰ *Sani Abacha v Gani Fawehinmi (2000) NWLR 228*

²¹ Umar, Abdul and Y, 'Analysis of Relevant Legal Frameworks on Child Protection in Malaysia and Nigeria'

²² World Health Organization, "Child Marriage" (2002) <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheet/details/child-marriage> accessed 17 March 2025

²³ G Girls Not Brides, "Causes of Child Marriage" (2020) <http://www.girlsnotbrides.org> accessed 17 March 2025

²⁴ Ibid

²⁵ United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (adopted 20 November 1989 entered into force 2 September 1990) 1577 UNITS 3(UNCRC); Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (Adopted 18 December 1979, entered into force 3 September 1981) 1249 UNTS 13 (CEDAW).

²⁶ United Nations, Sustainable Development Goals (2023) accessed 14 March 2025

²⁷ Human Rights Watch, No Way Out: Child Marriage and Human Rights Abuses, (2016)

²⁸ Plan International, The Impact of Child Marriage on Girls Education (2019) <https://plan-international.org> accessed 16 March 2025

mortality, complications during childbirth, psychological and emotional trauma.²⁹ In addition, child marriage perpetuates gender-based violence and limits women's autonomy, reinforcing patriarchal structures.³⁰ The economic burden of child marriage extends to national economies, as reduced workforce participation and healthcare costs impact overall national development.³¹

4. Causes and Consequences of Child Marriage

Abject poverty is one of the issues that compel parents to marry their girl children to affluent men to secure a living for both parents and children.³² There are also cases of loan redemption. In this case, the girl child may be held in bondage to a husband because of the inability of her parents to pay back loans. Religion, culture, and social norms. Many parents believe that early marriage helps to prevent and manage the promiscuity of the girl child.³³ In some religions and cultures, some parents eager to boost their self-esteem in many ramifications see child marriage as a fast way to increase their ego especially when it involves the affluent men. Teenage pregnancy is another cause of early marriage. pregnancy for some parents, rather than consider abortion, they opt for marriage as a way of sparing themselves and the girl child some embarrassment in society.³⁴

It is also crucial to note that Child marriage takes a heavy toll on the girl child. One of the major consequences of early marriage is the loss of childhood. Childhood is easily lost, obliterating opportunities for education and preparation for a happy and productive married life as they become mothers too easily. Right violation is another effect of early marriage.³⁵ The right to self-determination is undermined as parents pressure their children to yield to men who are not right for them. Due to immaturity and ignorance, the right to negotiate for sex and number of children is compromised. Impaired reproductive health. Lack of sexual education often leads to indiscriminate sex, abortion, delivery through operation, child/maternal mortality, and exposure to diseases such as STDs, HIV, and the dreaded Vesico-Vaginal Fistula (VVF) now ravaging the land. Stigmatization and abandonment are also other effects of early pregnancy.³⁶ Reproductive health impairment often brings shame, frustration, stigmatization, divorce, and eventual abandonment.

5. Appraisal of the Challenges and Enforcement of the Child Rights Act on Child Marriage

5.1 Child Rights Act 2003 on Child Marriage

The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) was ratified by Nigeria in 1991 and was subsequently enacted in 2003 by the National Assembly of Nigeria. The Act is contained in chapter 50, laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004. The CRA is enacted to protect the human rights of the child in general and, notably, prohibit child marriage, child betrothal, and unlawful sexual intercourse, among others. The purpose of this Act is to provide a uniform standard nationwide. Unfortunately, the 2003 Act is not without challenges. The intention behind the Child Rights Act was to localize the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child to guarantee the protection and promotion of children's rights. It has been twenty years since its enactment, but child marriage continues to occur in various sectors of Nigeria, thereby raising doubts as to whether the CRA truly works. One of the main challenges faced by the CRA is that it is not uniformly adopted across Nigeria. The Act may therefore be considered to have been passed at the federal level, but as stipulated in Section 12 of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria, any law passed by the National Assembly must be domesticated into state law for it to have full effect in that state. Thus, as of the year 2023, many northern states, especially the states where the practice of child marriage is more prevalent, have not been able to completely domesticate by adoption and thus implement the Act.

²⁹ WHO, Health Consequences of Child Marriage (2021) <https://www.who.int> accessed 16 March 2025

³⁰ UNFPA, Gender-Based Violence and Child Marriage (2002) <https://www.unfpa.org> accessed 17 March 2025

³¹ World Bank, Economic Impact of Child Marriage (2017) <https://www.worldbank.org> accessed 16 March 2025

³² O.J. Obasohan, Child Marriage in Nigeria (2015) Benson Idahosa University Law Journal Vol 2 No.1, p 571

³³ Ibid

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ Ibid

³⁶ Ibid

Even the differences between federal law and states' laws create a barrier to the enforcement of the CRA. The Nigerian Constitution, Section 29(4)(b), ambiguously indicates that “*any woman who is married shall be deemed to be of full age.*” This provision has been interpreted by some as a legal justification for the existence of child marriage. Such a constitutional provision, hence, creates a loophole in the law that detracts from the enforceability of the CRA's ban on child marriages. More of these legal issues will be discussed subsequently in this paper.

5.2 The Nexus Between the Child Rights Act 2003 and the Nigerian Constitution

Section 12 (1) of the 1999 constitution requires all treaties to be domesticated before creating a domestic legal obligation.³⁷ The CRA was promulgated by the National Assembly under its plenary powers to legislate for the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, but not for the Federation, since children are part of the residual list in the Nigeria constitution and, therefore, within the legislative preserve of states in the Nigerian Federation under section 12 (2) and (3) of the 1999 constitution.³⁸ Thus, domestic legislation on matters such as children (not on the exclusive legislative list) required the consent of the majority of the State Houses of Assembly of the Federation. Even if it became necessary for the 36 states to adopt the Act, it is vital to note that no state of the Federation is bound to adopt the CRA, and those that have done so did it at their discretion. As a result, 11 out of 36 states in Nigeria have yet to adopt the Act, making it inadequate and difficult to provide standard and necessary care, protection and rehabilitation for victims of early marriage throughout the country. Part III Section 21 of CRA states, “No person under 18 years can contract a valid marriage, and accordingly, a marriage so contracted is null and void and of no effect whatsoever.”³⁹ Pursuant to this, no parent, guardian or any other person shall betroth a child to any person”. In contravention of the above provision, the CRA provides punishment in III section 23 and views such contravention as criminal. The challenge here is that the above provisions still need to be binding on the states to domesticate CRA. The issue remains that, within a state that has not adopted CRA, child marriage will continue without penalties or sanction.

Furthermore, Part 1, item 61 of the second schedule of the Nigerian Constitution makes provision for the formation, annulment and dissolution of marriages other than marriages under the Islamic law and customary law, including matrimonial causes relating to it”.⁴⁰ The effect of the provision is that customary and Islamic law operate side by side with the Nigerian Constitution rather than bring into conformity with the provisions. Thus, customary law and Islamic law continue to operate as they are not affected by the ratification and subsequent domestication of various international instruments in Nigeria against child marriage. This provision is fortified by Nigeria's subscription to the principle of constitutional supremacy, which provides that the Nigerian Constitution is the supreme law of the land. Therefore, all laws enacted should be under the provision.

Under section 61 of part 1 of the second schedule to the 1999 Constitution, Islamic and customary marriages are not subject to any restrictions. Braimah, for instance, argues that there is a solid argument to be made that child marriage is not illegal in Nigeria under the second schedule section 61 part 1 of the Nigerian Constitution, which, as part of the exclusive legislative list, endows plenary powers on the formation, annulment and the dissolution of Islamic and Customary marriages on states of the federation since such marriages become part of the residual legislative list. He further states that:

“When a person marries a child under Islamic law in Northern Nigeria and is consequently in contravention of the Child Rights Act, such a person cannot be prosecuted because the federal government would be interfering with an Islamic marriage and would be in violation of part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution. Therefore, regarding child marriage, part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution serves as the supreme law of the land in Nigeria, overriding all other legislation”.⁴¹

³⁷ Section 12 (1) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

³⁸ Section 13 (2) and (3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

³⁹ Part 111, Section 21 of the Child Rights Act 2003

⁴⁰ Part 1, Section 6 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

⁴¹ Ibid

It is, therefore, an obvious fact that even though Nigeria's enactment of the CRA contains sections outlawing child marriage, there is a solid argument that child marriage is not illegal in Nigeria under Second Schedule Part 1 item 61 of the 1999 Constitution.

Again, as Nigeria operates a tripartite legal system with civil, customary and Islamic law operating simultaneously concerning marriage, the federal government has no control over customary and Islamic marriages but only over marriages conducted civilly. What this means is that, according to part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution, when a person marries a child under Islamic law in Northern Nigeria and is consequently in contravention of the CRA, such a person cannot be prosecuted because the federal government would be interfering with an Islamic marriage and would be in violation of part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution. Therefore, regarding child marriage, part 1, section 61 of the 1999 constitution renders the CRA useless as the 1999 constitution serves as the supreme law of the land in Nigeria, overriding all other legislation. An example of how part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution can be used as a constitutional backing for child marriage was shown in 2010, in Senator Ahmad Yerima's case. In this case, Ahmad Yerima married the daughter of his chauffeur, a 13-year-old Egyptian girl, after allegedly paying a dowry of \$100 000. Although the marriage created an uproar as it was in contravention of section 21 of the CRA, Yerima justified the marriage on religious grounds that:

‘Prophet Muhammad (SAW) married Aisha at the age of nine. Therefore, any Muslim who marries a girl of nine years and above follows the teachings and practices of Prophet Muhammad (SAW). If there is anybody who will tell me that what you did contradicts Islam, I will say I will submit, and I will do whatever they ask me to do.’

According to Tardzer, although Ahmad Yerima's conduct seemed reprehensible, there was nothing anyone could do about his marriage to the child. While Tardzer makes it clear that Yerima was never prosecuted, the Attorney-General of the Federation, Mohammed Bello Adoke, the then Attorney-General of Nigeria, maintained that because Ahmad Yerima's marriage was contracted under Islamic law, he would not face prosecution. Therefore, while Ahmad Yerima is in contravention of the CRA because his marriage is alleged to have taken place in Nigeria's Capital, Abuja, he cannot be prosecuted because the federal government would be in contravention of part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution. Consequently, it is a result of this constitutional provision that it is illegal and difficult to prosecute Ahmed Yerima for violating section 21 of the CRA. Furthermore, It seems, therefore, that while his assertion is correct that CRA 2003 may not be able to prosecute for child marriage, it is not only because of part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution but also because there is neither CPL nor other legislation that criminalizes child marriage in the manner of the CRA. For instance, section 15 (1) of the Jigawa State CRL 2006 prohibits child marriage but defines a child in section 2 (1) of the law as a person below puberty. Accordingly, it would be correct to state that Jigawa State criminalizes Child marriage to the extent that a girl has not reached puberty. This is possible as puberty is defined in section 2 of Jigawa law as the age at which a person is physically and psychologically capable of consummating a marriage. Furthermore, under section 15 (1) of the law, the court has the discretion to determine the puberty of the child bride according to the circumstances of each case. Thus, the absence of appropriate legislation immunizes Islamic or Customary marriages from the Bill of Rights because part 1 of the second schedule to the 1999 constitution merely defines how constituent parts of the federation share power.⁴² Because of the Supremacy Clause of the 1999 Constitution, such an exercise of power is subject to other parts of the Constitution, including the Bill of Rights.

Notably, Islamic or customary marriages are subject to the relevant human rights, and legislation such as the CPL could be struck down due to breaches of part of the Bill of Rights and, therefore, may be unconstitutional.⁴³ It would appear, therefore, that the CRA's provision of child marriage is ineffective because of this provision. It must be noted that in Nigeria, there is an evident struggle to balance guaranteeing the right to cultural/religious practices and applying international human rights law to protect human rights. Thus, while the CRA is seen as protecting the rights of children in Nigeria by

⁴² Nwabueze, B.O. Federalism in Nigeria under the Presidential Constitution (1983) 39

⁴³ Enyinna S. Nwwache: Child Marriage in Nigeria: Illegal and (UN) Constitutional (2015) 15 African Human Rights Law Journal 421 -432.

prohibiting child marriage on the one hand, on the other hand, the CRA prescription seems to be infringing on cultural/religious practices such as child marriage under Islam and Northern Nigeria where it is legal. This legality is backed by section 38 (1) of the Constitution, which entitles persons to freedom of thought, conscience and religion. This implies that CRA is at variance with the express rights of a group of persons to cultural and religious practices. This illustrates the fact that the prosecution of an Islamic or Customary marriage alleged to be a Child marriage is, invariably, a conflict between the right to freedom of religion, possibly in favour of the husband, and the other rights such as the right to personal liberty and the right to freedom of inhuman and degrading treatment.⁴⁴ An excellent example of this scenario is the marriage of Senator Yarima to a 13-year-old Egyptian girl. Therefore, while Ahmad Yerima is in contravention of the CRA because his marriage is alleged to have taken place in Nigeria's Capital, Abuja, he cannot be prosecuted because the federal government would be in contravention of part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution. Consequently, it is a result of this constitutional provision that it is illegal and difficult to prosecute Ahmed Yerima for violating section 21 of the CRA.

5.3 Sharia and Customary Court and Child's Rights Act 2003

Furthermore, creating state courts outside federal courts to entertain disputes emanating from customary/Islamic law constitutes a significant obstacle to applying international Human Rights Law and CRA 2003 against child marriage. Notably, the Sharia and customary courts in Nigeria are established by states to adjudicate matters bordering on customs and cultural practices. The foregoing illustrates the fact that the prosecution of an Islamic or Customary marriage alleged to be a Child marriage is, invariably, a conflict between the right to freedom of religion, possibly in favour of the husband, and other rights such as the right to personal liberty and the right to freedom of inhuman and degrading treatment.⁴⁵ Crucially, so long as these courts remain the sole guardians of customary law, cultural and religious practices legitimizing child marriage will be preserved. Giving these courts complete independence is a big obstacle to prohibiting child marriage. It will instead give way to the violation of human rights⁴⁶. For instance, the continuous application of customary laws runs afoul of guarantees in the international human rights conventions and treaties to which the federal state is a party and subsequent domestications such as the CRA. To avoid child marriage practices, customary courts should comply with basic human rights principles that abhor child marriage.

5.4 The Complexities of the Minimum Age

The minimum age of marriage is another serious challenge. Crucially, varieties of minimum age limits are problematic because they can cause discrimination between children of the same age in different parts of the country. Thus, CRA 2003 attempted to resolve some legal and practical impediments associated with the differential use of age of marriage and related punishments. By sections 21 and 23 of the CRA, it is illegal for a parent to marry off his or her daughter if she is below 18 years old. The same section provides a fine of ₦500,000:00 (or US \$ 700) or a jail term of 5 years.⁴⁷

Furthermore, it is punishable by imprisonment for a husband to consummate a marriage with a child under 18 years. He is deemed to have raped the child, who is considered to be illegally his wife under the provision of the Act. The CRA also provides that adopting non-biological children is permitted but that marrying an adopted son or daughter is null and void, with the punishment of up to 14 years in imprisonment. However, the contention around these sections of the law is enormous, especially with the uncoordinated definition of who a child is for this purpose. CRA define a child as a person who has not attained the age of 18 years⁴⁸ and consequently is not in a position to fully and freely enter into a marriage contract. Thus, section 2 of the Children and Young Persons Act (CYPA) States that "A child" means a person under the age of 14 years, while "a young person" means a person who has attained the age of 14 years and is under the age of 17 years. The Immigration Act stipulates that any person below 16 years is a

⁴⁴ Ibid

⁴⁵ Ibid

⁴⁶ Eboibi F.E.: The impact of federalism and legal pluralism on the Enforcement of International Human Rights law Against child marriage in Africa.

⁴⁷ Section 21 and 23 CRA 2003

⁴⁸ Nkoyo T: Revising Equality as a Right: The Minimum Age of Marriage clause in the Nigerian Child Rights Acts, 2003, Third World Quarterly, vol 27, No 7, PP 1299 – 1312, 2006, Routledge. P.1303

minor, whereas the Matrimonial Causes Act puts the age of maturity at 21 years. Crucially, with the introduction of Sharia law, the age of criminal responsibility became an issue and was variedly interpreted.⁴⁹ Unfortunately, these various provisions have created definitional uncertainty. The importance of a negotiated national minimum age for child marriage in Nigeria cannot be overstated, given the widespread recognition of the ills of child marriage.⁵⁰ It is necessary to work from and within Nigerian Muslim communities to agree on a minimum age for child marriage.

5.5 Contextual and Legal Complexities

Even though religious marriages are not trumps, they call for a nuanced consideration of their impact and, in the context of this article, require a determination of what qualifies as a child marriage, which is irrelevant in determining the extent to which the right to freedom of religion justifies or negates such a marriage. The use of 'puberty' as a threshold for child marriage invites consideration of biological characteristics.⁵¹ are as relevant as age in determining the capacity to marry.⁵² Comparative perspectives from India indicate that 'puberty' has been used as a threshold in determining when a girl child is fit for marriage. Accordingly, age could be a significant but not exclusive factor in determining marriage capacity. It appears plausible that the age of marriage could be negotiated in Nigeria. The importance of introducing flexibility in the age a child may be married is evident in the Constitution and statutory provisions that recognize a lower CRA-mandated age in Nigeria. First, section 29 (4) (b) of the 1999 Constitution provides that '(a)any woman who is married shall be deemed to be of full age.⁵³ Second, the CRL of Akwa Ibom State in south Nigeria defines a child as a person under 16. Regarding Muslim Nigeria, it would appear wrong to describe Muslims as a monolithic community that agreed on child marriages of girls under 18. To do that is to ignore the realities of the struggle within religious communities to overcome practices such as child marriages that would conform to orthodoxy. It is also to forget that the threshold of puberty offers a real opportunity to engage Muslims' scholarship and hierarchy in, for example, finding a threshold. It could be suggested, for instance, that a girl below 15 would not pass this threshold. Accordingly, the marriage of a girl between the ages of 15 and 18 years could be valid on the understanding that the girl is mature and understands the consequence of her actions. Comparative perspectives from India reveal that the threshold of puberty is the age of 15, and marriage at that age is voidable until the child is 18⁵⁴which is the age of consent. This is also the position of Islamic law in India.⁵⁵ An-Na'im has correctly argued that many interpretations exist in Islamic communities and that an engagement with progressive forces in these societies would achieve an interpretation of Islam that recognizes the dignity of all persons,⁵⁶ including children. Furthermore, it is suggested that legislation such as the Marriage Act, which is silent on the age permissible for marriage, needs to be modified to include the minimum age of 18. Under section 3 (1) (e), the Marriage Act merely provides that a marriage will be void if 'either of the parties is not of marriageable age. Similarly, like the Marriage Act, the Matrimonial Cause Act, which is also silent on a minimum age of marriage, should also be modified.

⁴⁹ Ibid

⁵⁰ See Iyabode O 'Child Bride and Child sex: combating child marriages in Nigeria' (2011) 2 Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence 85.

⁵¹ *Labinjoh v Abaka* 5 NLR 3 and *Folata v Dawomo* (1970) NWLR 105, Where the courts held that the contractual capacity of a child in Islamic law depends on physical capacity and maturity.

⁵² See MA Ambali *The practices Muslim family law in Nigeria* (2003) 155.

⁵³ See sec 29(4)(b) regarding the renunciation of citizenship. See also Azubuike Onuora-Oguno 'constitutionalizing the violation of the girl child in Nigeria: exploring constitutional safeguards and Pitfalls available at <http://www.ohrh.law.ox.ac.uk/constitutionalizing-the-violation-of-the-girl-child-in-nigeria-exploring-constitutional-safeguards-and-pitfalls/> (accessed 4 March 2024).

⁵⁴ Sec 2(a) of the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act 2006 declares a child as one who has not attained the age of 18

⁵⁵ See also *furquan v State* WP (CRL) 1025/2012.

⁵⁶ A An-Na'im 'Human rights in the Muslim world: Socio-political conditions and scriptural imperatives' (1990) 3 Harvard Human Rights Journal 13. See also I Ogunniran 'Child Rights Act versus Shari'a law in Nigeria: issues, challenges and way forward' (2010) 30 Children's Legal Rights Journal 62-80.

5.6 Weak Enforcement Mechanism

Weak Enforcement Mechanism is another serious challenge. Even where the Act has been domesticated, its enforcement becomes weak even among states due to poor institutional support and inadequate funding. Most law enforcement agencies do not have the necessary resources and training to effectively implement child protection laws. Even where they exist, there is often resistance among local authorities to prosecute cases of child marriage on account of cultural sensitivity and fear of backlash from influential community leaders.

The judicial process places further complications in that many victims of child marriage do not have access to legal representation or even an awareness of their rights under the CRA. High incidences of informal and traditional dispute resolution methods have also resulted in cases of child marriage being settled outside the formal court system, thus further incapacitating the operation of the Act.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Prohibition of child marriage remains a major challenge despite international efforts to eradicate it. While religious, customary, cultural and economic factors contribute to its persistence, legal and policy interventions are essential to ending the practice. This paper has indicated that despite Nigeria's adoption of the CRA, the Rights of the girl child regarding child marriage are not adequately protected by law. Firstly, this inadequacy stems from the approach taken by those states in Nigeria that have to domesticate the CRA before it applies in those states. Secondly, part 1, section 61 of the 1999 constitution, which provides that the federal government cannot interfere with Islamic and Customary marriages, weakens and fails to give effect to the CRA to protect children against a social evil such as child marriage. Although the wording of part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution gives people the freedom to conduct marriages according to their religion and customs, it is a dangerous clause which serves as a loophole for child marriages and serves as constitutional support to those who partake in child marriage and justify it as an Islamic practice. Thus, one of the main hurdles in the CRA 2003, inadequate protection of the girl child from child marriage in Nigeria, is found in part 1, section 61 of the 1999 constitution. Other challenges leading to the persistent widespread of this barbaric practice are religious resistance and cultural differences, poor enforcement, and socio-economic challenges. In addition, lack of clarity regarding the age of marriage and the definition of a child as contained in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Child's Rights Act 2003, lack of effective implementation of international laws in respect of child marriage in Nigeria, the prerogative of signing, adopting and enforcing international treaties which are that of the federal government as well as lack of awareness raising among others. Thus, in the struggle to ensure that child marriages are prohibited and curbed, the researcher will make the following recommendation:

1. Involvement of the relevant stakeholders to raise awareness of the social economic and health hazards of child marriages. Not only should the government and stakeholders make efforts to see that the legal enactment is successfully implemented and adhered to, but their efforts in raising awareness are also paramount.

2. To prevent child marriage, part 1 section 61 of the 1999 constitution needs to be modified to involve the federal government in 'the formation, annulment and dissolution of all marriages, including customary and Islamic marriages.

3. The Nigerian legislature must promulgate the marriageable age as 18 years for women in the 1999 constitution. The implication is that since the 1999 Constitution serves as the supreme law of the land, any traditional or religious marriage practice that contravenes the age of marriage in the 1999 Constitution will be void. This will provide an objective rather than a subjective standard of maturity, thereby safeguarding a child from being married when they are not physically, mentally and emotionally ready. More so, they can give free and full consent to marry as they would have possessed the minimum level of maturity needed before marriage.

4. Religious and traditional/community leaders should be made to understand the adverse effects of child marriage ranging from the health implications and lack of education, which in turn puts them in a disadvantaged position in future.

5. There is a need to enact a 'Prohibition of Child Marriage Act', which deals broadly with the issue of child marriage.
6. The Marriage Act, which is silent on the age permissible for marriage, must be modified to include the minimum age of 18. Again, under section 3 (1) (e), the Marriage Act merely provides that a marriage will be void if 'either of the parties is not of marriageable age. Similarly, like the Marriage Act, the Matrimonial Cause Act, which is also silent on a minimum age of marriage, should also be modified.
7. Universal Domestication and Constitutional Amendment is very necessary. All states should be encouraged to domesticate the CRA, as well as to amend the Constitution of Nigeria in order to weed out any ambiguities that can be advanced as justification for child marriage.
8. Community Engagement and Awareness is also crucial. Grassroots advocacy campaigns involving religious and local leaders should be initiated to change cultural perceptions toward child marriage.